

THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICINE IN THE CALIPHATE OF CORDOBA

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Annotatsiya.

Ushbu maqolada Qurdoba xalifaligidagi ilm-fan rivojlanishiga ilib kelgan omillar va bunda xalifalarning o'rni va ahamiyati, X-XI asrlarda Cordobada tibbiyot fanining ravnaq topishi va kasalxonalar faoliyati haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar.

Tibbiyot, az-Zahraviy, kasalxona, Abdurahmon III, Ibn Rushd, Ibn Tufayl, Ibn Sino, Javod an-Nasroniy, jarroxlilik

Аннотация.

В данной статье говорится о факторах, обусловивших развитие науки в Куртубинском халифате, о роли и значении халифов, развитии медицинской науки и функционировании больниц в Куртубе в X-XI веках.

Ключевые слова.

Медицина, аз-Захрави, больница, Абдуррахман III, Ибн Рушд, Ибн Туфайл, Ибн Сина, Джавад ан-Насрани, хирургия.

Annotation.

This article talks about the factors that led to the development of science in the Caliphate of Cordoba, the role and importance of the caliphs, the development of medical science and the operation of hospitals in Cordoba in the X-XI centuries.

Key words.

Medicine, al-Zahrawi, hospital, Abdurrahman III, Ibn Rushd, Ibn Tufail, Ibn Sina, Javad al-Nasrani, surgery.

With the emergence of Islam, it began to spread to large countries in a short period of time. One of the commandments given to Prophet Muhammad (s.a.v) when Islam was delivered was to spread Islam to as many people as possible and to as many lands as possible. In this direction. The four caliphs, the Umayyads, the Abbasids, and later the Turkic states that adopted Islam from the time of Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) aimed to protect Islam and bring it to a large number of people by adopting the idea of Islamic Jihad.

One of the most important of these conquests is the conquests in Africa and Europe. During the Umayyad period, territories such as Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia were occupied on the African continent and were called the Maghrib. With the conquest of 710, Andalusia became an Islamic country. One of the important cities of the Iberian Peninsula, Cordoba was under Roman and Goth rule for many years. Cordoba, which became an Islamic city with the conquests that took place in this area at the beginning of the 8th century, became the center of the Andalusian governorate of the Umayyad caliphate in the early years, and with the establishment of the Umayyad state in the middle of the 8th century, Andalusia became the capital. From the beginning of the 10th century, when the rulers of Andalusia received the title of "caliph", Cordoba also became the center of the caliphate (Appendix 1). During this period, Cordoba was one of the most important cities of both the Islamic world and Europe.

Health has been one of the most important needs since the dawn of mankind, as basic needs as food and shelter. Humanity history during health problems solution to do for different methods used In this process some are stone, tree , soil or plants treatment for others use it magic , like a prayer of methods used Other from their side some of them such treatment methods to use did not approve of this them created To God against rebellion to be they thought it was possible . Even medicine surgery field Underrated in Europe and only butchers and hairdressers by done to be increased occupation as seen _ _ For example , in the city of Tours in France in 1163 Council from surgery only hairdresser and butchers engage in , all medicine schools and respectable people this from activity give up pass said that it is necessary to the decision the bride came ¹³⁴.

Medium in centuries in Europe backward health storage field seen if , on the contrary , this in the Islamic world at the time this in the field big changes face gave Strong the brain inflammation another sharp from infections separate standing to meningitis diagnosis to put and treatment possible was ¹³⁵

Muslims Pyrenees from conquest after long one lifetime medicine with they didn't do it . with tib in Andalus " Muahidun " class of practitioners was ¹³⁶. One of the first doctors one Khalid ibn Yazid ibn Roman an- Nasrani be during the time of Amir Muhammad to the eye seen doctor was Javad an Nasrani and Hamdin ibn Eba, ibid period lived famous christian doctors is between The first Muslim of doctors growing up output to the era of Amir Muhammad right _ will come

¹³⁴ Salim.T . Al-Hassani. 1001 inventions. The enduring legacy of Muslim civilization. - Washington: National Geographic Society, 2012. - P. 156.

¹³⁵ Sigrid H. Avrupa'nın Üzerine Doğan İslam Güneşi. – İstanbul. Bedir yayinevi, 1972. – S. 167..

¹³⁶ Mehmet Özdemir. Endülüs Müslümanları. – İstanbul: Türkiye Diyanet Vakfı, 2020. –S. 67-69

Periods tooth with islam in medicine to the eye seen persons growing up came out , each of them that's it of the period the most advanced medical pamphlets created and thus medicine theory and of practice new direction to determine help gave Interesting that is Andalusia the most famous Philosophers are also doctors was Among them Ibn Tufail, Ibn Rushd and another Jew doctors there is was _ Aristotle reviewer as known as Ibn Rushd how much medical works , including " About medicine common data book " encyclopedia and Ibn Sina's medical to his works comments with famous Maimonides to 10 medicine about work wrote , that's all Arabic in the language

In Andalusia medicine in the field attention owner from the changes one is that some doctors today's in the day that it was such as to patients to look for personal to practice rooms have were to the notes according to this period doctor being worked by Ibn Mulukin-Nasrani patients waiting get and treatment for one the house to the office turned and to his patients treatment until he turn sit down for thirty a chair put.

In Andalusia in the field of medicine in the XI century lived doctors , Zahrawi ratio with famous Abul Qasim Khalaf ibn Abbas al - Zahrawi being Caliph Abdurrahman III, Hakam II and During the reign of Hisham II in the palace activity conducted. Life about enough information preserved not left " Kitab-ut Tasrif li-man ajaza ". work writing left _ First living past _ Greek and Muslim of doctors from his works fruitful used without own creativity the product to the middle put .

The first studies in the field of medicine in the Islamic world, It began during the time of Muhammad (s.a.v) and reached its peak during the four caliphs, the Umayyads and the Abbasids. The caliphs showed great sensitivity in this regard and invited the surrounding statesmen and rich people to contribute to this field. In addition to providing free services to patients in these hospitals, additional assistance such as beds, food, clothing and material assistance was provided during the recovery period. Later, hospitals were divided into fixed, mobile, leprosy, etc., and sections for men and women were also built separately. In addition to being used as a place to serve patients, these areas became a facility that provided medical education and housed students. In addition, libraries containing a large number of books were established and scientific discussions were held, these spaces also served as a center for the exchange of knowledge and experience of judges and students. All opportunities have been created for doctors to receive good medical education and develop their profession. In fact, special funds have been allocated so that doctors can have a good standard of living. These medical

studies in the Islamic world contributed greatly to the medical science of today, and especially during the Crusades, Europeans had the opportunity to witness and enjoy this civilization. Hospitals were not limited to some regions of the medieval Islamic world, but spread to large cities such as Baghdad, Damascus, Cairo, and the Umayyads of Andalusia. The patients were provided close to modern health care services in the hospitals built with special care, rising to the heights of medical science. Private funds were allocated to these hospitals, and free services were provided to the patients there. In addition, along with the provision of these services, health services are provided to foreigners regardless of religion, language and race.

Andalusia has its own hospitals network with famous is medium in centuries the most advanced calculated . To the sources relying on to say if we are , only one 50 hospitals in Cordoba and 900 congregations bathrooms there is was medieval centuries of Islam another big in cities that it was as in Andalusia hospitals are also ours modern study from our hospitals different like education place also played the role .

Islamic world of hospitals main of duties one patients language , religion and of race difference without doing treatment was Other side , rich or poor al be it , all to patients free of charge service was shown and this service for no money was required . In addition , healthy eating during was , but this period material in terms of recreation , needs to satisfy opportunity didn't happen to patients known amount payment and one layer clothes given _ in Bimaristan to patients bed , food and medicines are also free service as offer done. These costs bimaristans organize when done income to bimaristans gift done land and farmer farms at the expense of covered

Plants patients maintenance to do and treatment such as main of duties besides , educational and practical also have tasks was Doctors are also teachers acted as and patients to see during own students themselves with take They left , that's it while to his students themselves closely observation enable gave. So students doctors with patients with talk , see and treatment methods study , wrote recipes thorough performance , professor teachers with the disease discussion to do possible have it happened So students medical education when they started , they diary clinical experiences because of practical medicine to the experience have has been enough _information have without being the patient to treatment attempt was found to be a fraud . Doctors of students to class to go table based on follow this separately attention they looked Doctors one in the place the work start for

official documents or today's day to the conditions according to diplomas present reach need was It is official in Spain as well as in Baghdad the law as used ¹³⁷.

Doctors and medicine students this to the ground come and take lessons will be held and one how many interesting medical things discussion to do possible have will be This is a conference halls on the wall tall cabinets time tooth with to medicine about many manuscripts with equipped and medicine students of them enjoy were ¹³⁸.

In Europe the sick treatment concept East from the world completely different was For example , leprosy in 1490 with sick spiritual patient for blasphemy to torture judgment done ¹³⁹. Andalusia minister Lisaneddin Ibn Ibn Mrs his " Ihata Fi Akhbar _ Girnata " in the book note to what according to Andalusia Muslims emir Muhammad ibn Yusuf ibn Ismail ibn Faraj ibn Ismail ibn Faraj ibn Yusuf ibn Nasr to the Emirates necessity and to the need despite the former rulers did not work did Of these except bathrooms , warehouses , toilets , caravanserais , residences places built . He built hospital in Egypt hospitals style it's like and inside ventilation There is also a system was historian Saladin is Bimaristan is called " square". in the form of , in Cairo Kalawun from bimari harder and wider not , but it is simpler , but more organized and more subtle to the details he describes as having " . This is in Bimaristan one the field around halls there is was In the middle of the field deep pool and two spring there is was in the pool sitting two of the lion from his mouth water would come In 1492 Granada from the Arabs pulling if taken , this small building to the mint converted . Later it was changed a little time after destroyed it happened ."

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